

BASE	STRING	ART. RETORNADOS	ART. ACEITOS
Revista Ensino & Pesquisa	"aprendizagem tangencial" AND "videogames"	0	0
ACM	"tangential learning" AND (videogames OR "video games" OR games) AND education	2	0
AJET	"tangential learning"	0	0
BJET	"tangential learning"	0	0
C&E	"tangential learning"	0	0
CAIS	"tangential learning"	0	0
CBIE	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
CSBC - WEI	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
CTRL + E	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
Computer on the Beach	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
DesafIE!	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
EJIS (Taylor & Francis Group)	"tangential learning" AND (videogames OR "video games" OR games) AND education	2	1
ERIC	"tangential learning" AND (use OR method OR application) AND(videogames OR "video games" OR games)	2	1
ICTE	Busca Manual	1	1
IEEE			
IEEE TLT		3	0
IEEE ToE			
IHE	"tangential learning"	5	2
JETHE	"tangential learning"	0	0
ISJ	"tangential learning"	3	0
InfEdu	"tangential learning"	0	0
JCThink	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
JMIS	"tangential learning"	0	0
RBIE	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
RENOTE	"aprendizagem tangencial"	1	0
RITA	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
Redin	"aprendizagem tangencial"	0	0
Revista Docência e Ciberultura:	("tangential learning") AND ("use" OR "method") AND ("videogames" OR "video games" OR "g	0	0
Revista Informática na Educação: teoria & pr	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
Revista de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia	("tangential learning") AND ("use" OR "method") AND ("videogames" OR "video games" OR "g	0	0
Revista principia - IFPB	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
Revistas IFG	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
Revistas PUC SP	SEM ACESSO	-	-
SBGAMES	BUSCA MANUAL NOS ANAIS	0	0
SBIE	("tangential learning") AND ("use" OR "method") AND ("videogames" OR "video games" OR "g	0	0
SCOPUS	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	5	2
T&F CSE	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
Tand FILE	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
TandF CSE	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
WIE	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
j-ets	"aprendizagem tangencial" OR "tangencial learning"	0	0
simpósio hipertexto e tecnologias na edu	("tangential learning") AND ("use" OR "method") AND ("videogames" OR "video games" OR "g	1	1
simpósio SJEEC	("tangential learning") AND ("use" OR "method") AND ("videogames" OR "video games" OR "g	1	1
IOJES	("tangential learning") AND ("use" OR "method") AND ("videogames" OR "video games" OR "g	1	1
TOTAL:		27	10